

PROCESS CONSIDERATIONS FOR LIQUID MOLDING OF COMPOSITES BASED ON ANIONIC POLYAMIDE 6

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ABSTRACT

Alongside liquid molding of thermoset-based composites, liquid molding of thermoplastic resins is currently receiving attention. The different natures of both materials however, prohibit one to one copying of processes such as vacuum injection and Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). The influence of crystallization and rapid polymerization of Anionic Polyamide 6 on process parameters such as temperature, pressure and injection time as well as compatibility problems with currently available fibers are discussed in the presented paper. It will be shown that the basic material properties hold the key in designing successful liquid molding processes.

Key terms: Vacuum injection, RTM, thermoplastic resin, anionic polyamide 6

INTRODUCTION

Liquid molding processes such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) and vacuum injection form the mainstay of thermoset based composite manufacturing. Injection strategies, process parameters and simulation were given significant attention in the past decades, resulting in well-developed manufacturing processes. Recent attention is drawn towards liquid molding of thermoplastic resins such as Anionic Polyamide 6 [1] and 12 [2], and Cyclic PBT [3,4]. Although parallels exist with liquid molding of for instance epoxies and vinyl esters, it must not be forgotten that polymer morphology and rheokinetics differ significantly for these thermoplastic resins, requiring modifications to the current liquid molding processes or development of new ones. This paper discusses the phenomena to be encountered when applying casting grade Anionic Polyamide 6 (APA6) in liquid molding processes in general and in vacuum injection in particular. Material properties and process parameters are discussed sequentially.

MATERIAL PROPERTIES

In this section the material characteristics of casting grade APA6 are discussed as well as its compatibility with reinforcing fibers.

Anionic Polyamide 6: The anionic polymerization of caprolactam into polyamide 6 (PA6) is a catalyzed reaction at 130-190°C and is completed in 1-60 minutes depending on the initiator/catalyst system used [5]. Throughout the text, ϵ -Caprolactam in combination with “C-10” Sodium

Fig. 1: DSC scan of APA6, heat rate: +10°C/min, cool rate -+10°C/min

Caprolactamate catalyst and “C-20” Carbamoylcaprolactam initiator supplied by DSM the Netherlands is referred to as APA6 throughout the text, unless stated differently. Due to the short polymerisation times, this system is very suitable for casting (near) final shape parts directly from the monomer melt. Prior to casting, the caprolactam monomer is molten and mixed with the initiator/catalyst system at 100°C and injected into a mould, which is preheated at 130 - 190°C. Having a melting temperature of 220°C, solid PA6 is obtained during polymerization. Due to simultaneous crystallization, crystals are withdrawn from the solution during polymerization, resulting in an increase in catalyst and initiator concentration in the solution. Consequently the reaction rate increases during polymerization, which is often (perhaps erroneously) labeled as the “autocatalytic effect” [6]. Since the catalyst is sensitive to moisture and at elevated temperatures caprolactam is sensitive to oxidation, processing and storage should take place in a dry (and preferably) nitrogen environment.

PA6 anionically polymerized from solution has a higher degree of crystallinity compared to the same material crystallized from the melt as is shown in the DSC scan in figure 1. In addition, due to the anionic character of the polymerization combined with the possibility of chain branching, a higher MW is obtained compared to hydrolytically formed PA6. As a result, modulus, density, chemical resistance, wear resistance, creep resistance, glass transition (T_g) and dimensional stability of APA6 are, depending on the degree of crystallinity, higher than of PA6 [7].

Fig. 2: Mechanical properties of samples cut at various distances from the resin inlet (ASTM D 790M 3-point bending test)

Compatibility with fibers: Prior to weaving, a direct coating or sizing is applied to the fibers to improve fiber handling. Afterwards, a second (indirect) coating or coupling agent is applied to improve the interaction between the fibers and the matrix. Additional requirement to these additives is that they do not negatively influence the properties of the final composite. Various fiber/additive combinations are available suitable for *in situ* polymerization of thermoset resins and for melt processing of thermoplast resins. Being applied only recently in combination with fiber reinforcement, a fiber/additive combination suitable for *in situ* polymerization of thermoplastic resins has not been developed as such. Unsuitable additives on the fibers might react with either catalyst or initiator, reducing the concentration of active groups in the solution during resin flow. As a consequence, final monomer conversion in the composite will decrease along the flow path of the resin from regions with maximum conversion down to regions in which no polymerization has taken place as all. A dramatic decline in mechanical properties away from the resin inlet is obvious, as is shown in figure 2. Existing fiber/additive combinations can be made suitable for APA6 by modifying the applied sizing. Table 1 shows the resulting improvements in mechanical properties for Glass with an experimental sizing supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composites the Netherlands. In the same table, SEM pictures of the fiber matrix interface clearly demonstrate that without sizing modification the final degree of conversion is less. Residual monomer is removed during polishing of the SEM samples, leaving voids behind.

Unmodified		Modified	
E-Modulus [Gpa]	Strength [MPa]	E-Modulus [Gpa]	Strength [Mpa]
9.6	306	19.8	580

The SEM image shows a cross-section of a fiber matrix interface. The fibers are visible as dark, irregular shapes against a lighter matrix. There are significant voids and gaps between the fibers and the matrix, indicating poor adhesion. A scale bar at the bottom right indicates 500 μm. Technical data at the bottom left includes: Acc.V 15.0 kV, Spot 5.0, Magn 50x, Det SE, WD 11.3, Exp 1, TC4082 ongesp apa6 150 C.

Table 1: Differences in mechanical properties (ASTM D 790M 3-point bending test) and degree of conversion (SEM) before and after sizing modification.

PROCESS PARAMETERS

In this section the influence of material properties of APA6 on the process parameters (temperature, pressure and injection time) are discussed.

Temperature: In figure 3, time to viscous, crystallization initiation time and time to complete crystallization are presented as function of the polymerization temperature. The time to viscous is a measure for the speed of polymerization and is reached at about 20 % caprolactam conversion [5]. At this point a big increase in viscosity takes place. Hence, before reaching time to viscous, impregnation of the entire product has to be completed. Below 128 °C, this impregnation boundary is formed by the crystallization initiation time.

Although below 130 °C, the impregnation window is less narrow, the tendency to crystallize is such that reactive groups are withdrawn from the solution and become trapped in the crystals. As a result, final conversion is low and the morphology is badly developed, leading to weak mechanical properties.

Fig. 3: Various stages during polymerization as function of temperature (Source: DSM)

At temperature above 140 °C, the speed of polymerization increases, leading to a short impregnation time, whereas the total time to complete the reaction (= the time to complete crystallization) increases. This is especially true for thick parts, in which the heat of the exothermal reaction can cause a temperature rise towards the melting point of polyamide 6, hence decreasing the tendency to crystallize.

The thermal conductivity of the polymerizing mixture is relatively low and as a consequence for thick walled laminates the temperature in the center can increase with approximately 55 °C due to the exothermal polymerization reaction. Therefore, at polymerization temperatures above 165 °C, the temperature can locally exceed the melting temperature of polyamide 6 ($T_m = 220\text{ °C}$), with the following consequences:

1. *Decrease in crystallinity*: The part of the polyamide 6, which crystallizes from the melt will have a lower degree of crystallinity compared to the polyamide 6 crystallized from solution, see figure 1. In addition, melt crystallized polyamide 6 contains besides α -structure crystals also γ -structure crystals, which have a lower modulus and a lower melting point.

Fig. 4: (caprolactam \rightleftharpoons polyamide 6) equilibrium as function of temperature (Source: DSM)

2. *Shift in reaction equilibrium:* The equilibrium (caprolactam \leftrightarrow polyamide 6) is temperature dependent as is shown in figure 4. Due to this equilibrium, final degree of conversion at elevated temperatures is reduced. Below T_m of polyamide 6, the caprolactam remains in the polyamide matrix, acting as softening agent. Above T_m the Caprolactam fraction is such that it can cause depolymerization in case the gaseous monomer is removed from the solution as is shown in the TGA graph in figure 5.

For the system presented, the ideal starting temperature for injection seems to be 140 °C.

Fig. 5: TGA scan of APA 6 below T_m (200°C) and above T_m (250°C)

Pressure: In general, the lower the pressure the faster the impregnation and the better the compaction and impregnation of the fibers. However, when injecting low molecular weight monomer at elevated temperatures in vacuum, volatile evaporation has to be prevented. The relation between evaporation pressure and temperature according to Clausius-Clapeyron [8] for caprolactam is presented in figure 6. In case the applied vacuum is lower than the vaporation pressure, caprolactam starts to boil and leaves voids in the final composite, see figure 7 [1]. An ideal injection pressure seems to be 200 mbar.

Fig. 6: Temperature – Vaporation pressure relation according to Clausius-Clapeyron

Fig. 7: SEM picture of sample injected at high vacuum (10 mbar injection pressure at 160 °C)

Injection time: The curing time for thermoset resins is considerably longer than its impregnation time during vacuum injection, in contrast to the fast polymerizing anionic polyamide 6. As a consequence, rheokinetics play a more predominant role during injection in case of APA6 and polymerization time will more often be the limiting factor to the maximum achievable product dimensions.

Temperature significantly influences the impregnation time as is discussed previously, but cannot be chosen freely to obtain a suitable injection window, since a set injection temperature is prescribed to obtain good material properties; in our case 140 °C. Changing the concentration of activator or catalyst will influence the reaction rate but will also influence the final degree of conversion and MW, hence altering the final materials properties.

Besides on the injection temperature and the initial concentration of activegroups, the reaction rate also depends on the type of initiator and catalyst used, see table 2. The fact that a solution of a metal caprolactamate in caprolactam is hardly dissociated results in the difference in activity of the various catalyst/initiator combinations. Due to the bad dissociation, the reaction can only take place due to the fact that in the right combination of initiator and catalyst, a complex is formed between the activator and the cation of the catalyst and, as a result, anions will be set free. Upon reaching a certain anion threshold concentration, reaction rate and viscosity suddenly increase. Both the geometry and the electric forces of initiator and cation determine the possibility for complexation. It takes longer for less compatible catalyst/initiator combinations to reach this threshold for fast polymerization. The remaining reaction however proceeds as fast as for more compatible catalyst/initiator combinations.

Catalyst	Initiator	Acylcaprolactam		Carbamoylcaprolactam	
		Aliphatic	Aromatic	Aliphatic	Aromatic
Sodium caprolactamate		21	21	3	31
Potassium caprolactamate		7	7	2.5	3.5
Bromomagnesium caprolactamate		2	2	20	20
Magnesium-bis-caprolactamate		>60	>60	>60	>60

Table 2: Total polymerization time for various catalyst/initiator combinations (Conditions: 1 mole% catalyst, 1 mole% activator, T_{mix} 100°C, T_{mould} 140°C.) (Source: DSM)

Figure 8: Viscosity profiles for a slow reacting system and a fast reacting system.

In figure 8, a typical viscosity profile (“exponential” [5]) for a fast reacting system and a slow reacting system are presented. These profiles can be combined with Darcy’s law [10] for flow through porous media to predict resin flow in between the fibers, see equation 1.

$$\frac{Q}{A} = \frac{K \Delta P}{\eta L} \quad (1)$$

In which Q/A is the resin flow rate per unit area [m], K the reinforcement permeability [m^2], ΔP the applied pressure [Pa] and L the flow front progression [m]. Flow front progression during injection of a rectangular strip, derived from equation 1, is presented in equation 2 [11].

$$L(t) = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot K \cdot \Delta P \cdot t}{\varphi \cdot \eta}} \quad (2)$$

In which φ is the porosity of the reinforcement [-]. Flow front propagation, figure 9, is calculated using equation 2. ($K = 1 \cdot 10^{-10} m^2$, $\varphi = 0.55$ “8-harness satin glass”, $\Delta P = 0.8 \cdot 10^5 Pa$ “Vacuum injection”, $\Delta P = 8 \cdot 10^5 Pa$ “RTM”). Depending on the product dimensions, a suitable catalyst/initiator system can be chosen to complete impregnation just before the time to viscous is reached. This way, full impregnation is obtained at the lowest cycle time. As can be seen in figure 9, an impregnation depth of only 27 cm can be obtained with the fast reacting system, which makes it in general unsuitable for this manufacturing technique.

CONCLUSIONS

It was shown that when designing a liquid molding process for APA6-based composites, process parameters need to be chosen carefully. Temperature must be controlled accurately to obtain a high degree of conversion and crystallization, whilst preventing internal temperature peaks to cause material degradation. Pressure is limited to the vaporation pressure at the chosen temperature to prevent evaporation of monomer prior to polymerization. Depending on the product dimensions, a

suitable catalyst/initiator system can be chosen to complete impregnation just before the time to viscous is reached. This way, full impregnation is obtained at the lowest cycle time.

Fig. 9: Time-flow front propagation data for APA6 in vacuum injection ($\Delta P = 0.8 \cdot 10^5$ Pa) and RTM ($\Delta P = 8 \cdot 10^5$ Pa) for a slow and a fast reacting system

For APA6, initial process parameters for vacuum injection are determined. To obtain good matrix properties the initial polymerization temperature (T_0) is set at 140°C. Taking the temperature rise during polymerization in account, the minimum injection pressure (P) is set at 200 mbar. A catalyst/initiator system, which results in a slow reaction needs to be applied. It was shown that currently available fiber/additive combinations are not suitable for liquid molding of thermoplastic resins. A sizing modification is necessary to reach high conversion rates and a well-developed fiber-matrix interface. Based on these process parameter, suitable vacuum injection equipment is developed, which is presented in [1].

AKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to thank DSM Fiber Intermediates (Geleen, the Netherlands) for supplying the APA6 resin systems and information, and and Ten Cate Advanced Composites (Nijverdal, the Netherlands) for supplying the glass fibers.

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